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GAMEHEARTS

Ethical Approval

Project: Games, Heritage, Arts, & Sport: the economic, social, and cultural value of the European video game ecosystem. GAMEHEARTS

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1. Project Summary

GAMEHEARTS seeks to maximise the value of the European video game industry ecosystems (hereafter, EVGIE) within a wider social context of the creative and cultural industries (hereafter, CCI). This considers the importance of the EVGIE in contributing to economic growth, job creation, physical and mental wellbeing, and social and cultural cohesion, by particularly focusing on how a stronger and closer working relationship between the traditional and emergent cultural sectors, can work better to create more inclusive and socially responsible cultural experiences. The consortium offers policy recommendations and roadmaps setting out the ways in which the EVGIE can and should develop, and where it could act as a driver for sustained innovation and economic growth. It utilises an evidence-based approach that focuses not just on video game development, but rather adopts a comprehensive ecosystem approach, working with both established and more innovative methodologies, to consider the competitiveness and development of the EVGIE, and the ways in which video game know-how and technologies could drive innovation in the wider CCI. In doing so, GAMEHEARTS develops 'ludic experiences', to explore possibilities of more inclusive, engaging, and empowering cultural experiences. Working across seven work packages the universities of Vienna (coordinator) (Austria), Salford (UK), Tampere (Finland), Breda University of Applied Sciences (Netherlands), and Wroclaw University of Economics and Business (Poland) work in partnership with Imperial War Museum (UK), City Football (UK), Ubisoft (France), and other major video game partners and associations (including the Video Games Europe (VGE) & European Video Games Developer Federation (EGDF)) to explore current and future trends in the EVGIE. Beyond this, GAMEHEARTS works with certain cultural case studies partners to consider the ways in which game-related technologies and practices are, and could be used to, increase access to heritage, the arts, and sport.

2. Research Ethics as a Comprehensive and Continuous Process

In establishing the ethical foundation for GAMEHEARTS research project, the GAMEHEARTS consortium is fully committed to upholding fundamental values and ensuring compliance with the highest ethical standards throughout the entire project lifecycle. Our approach is characterised by continuous evaluation and mitigation of potential ethical and legal challenges, with a particular focus on respecting human dignity, freedom, democracy, equality, and human rights, including the rights of minorities as outlined in EU values. We embed the adherence to ethical-legal frameworks in every aspect of our project tasks, under the close supervision of the project coordinator, reflecting our dedication to ethical integrity. We embrace a holistic perspective and approach ethics as a processual rather than an action, which is fixed in time. Hence, the consortium undertakes research with the understanding that ethics are subject to continuous reflection and evaluation with regard to impacts on and rights of subjects as well as research integrity and researchers' ethical standing. The first rule of 'no harm' is paramount in the research design and application of the project. Organisationally, there are specific processes fixed in time according to internal and other guidelines for the implementation of the project. In addition to those, however, researchers consider various ethical dimensions, including intersectionality, women's rights, gender equality, and the protection of children, minors, and minority rights.

Our proactive stance includes anticipating and managing potential vulnerabilities associated with digitisation and innovation. By adopting a comprehensive ethical framework, we ensure conscientious execution of our research endeavours, considering not only individual beliefs and principles but also the broader societal context.

From this comprehensive standpoint, we integrate considerations of historical, social, and other vulnerabilities to avoid perpetuating discriminatory positions and uphold principles of equality and human dignity.

Our commitment extends to ensuring that our research activities have an exclusive focus on civil applications, prohibiting contributions to military purposes or violations of any aspect of human rights and fundamental freedoms. Moreover, we are dedicated to the dissemination of knowledge, emphasising open access to research for future generations. Our research materials will be made accessible to the ability we have and with safeguards towards human subjects of our research to the academic community, practitioners, policymakers, and societal stakeholders, in order to foster collaboration and contribute to the advancement of knowledge.

3. Ethical Standards and Legislative Alignment

In adherence to ethical principles and relevant legislations, GAMEHEARTS commits to the following:

- a. Full compliance with the European Code of Conduct for research Integrity published by the All-European Academies, ensuring that no activities excluded from funding will be carried out.
- b. Application of the same ethical standards in countries outside the EU, such as the United Kingdom, ensuring alignment with the European Code of Ethics.
- c. No compromise on the integrity of data or information included in the proposal.
- d. Commitment to addressing potential ethical issues through periodic revisions at various stages of the research.
- e. The Consortium has designated an Ethics Officer, under Point 6.1. “General Structure” of the Consortium Agreement. The officer, an internal member of the consortium, will be consulted on any ethical considerations. Any significant concerns raised by the officer will promptly be communicated to the Project Officer and the consortium. Additionally, the officer is tasked with periodically reviewing European and national ethical guidelines and updating the consortium accordingly. The officer is supported by the Deputy Ethics Officer.
- f. Acknowledgement of the low-risk nature of the research planned in countries outside the EU, with measures in place to address any unforeseen ethical challenges. The research team remains vigilant and will engage in ongoing discussions and reflection to address any unforeseen ethical challenges that may arise. The ethics officer(s), consortium members, and host research institutions will offer support and guidance in handling such situations. In highly unlikely extreme cases, guidance may be sought from the Commission.

4. Ensuring Ethical Integrity in Human Participation and Data Handling

Maintaining ethical integrity in our research constitutes a pivotal element of GAMEHEARTS' methodology. Our project embraces an evidence-based approach, adopting a holistic perspective on the competitiveness and development of the European Video Game Industry Ecosystem (EVGIE). The methodology is interdisciplinary, employing a multi-sector, mixed method approach, including case studies and multi-informant, multinational ecosystem research.

Human participation is designed as participation in focus groups, interviews, participation in designing applications, participation in round-table formats and contribution to research design as well as execution. Standard ethic codes regarding the protection of mental and physical health of individuals while engaged in any of the aspects described, respect to fundamental rights and right to withdrawal, appropriate processes of protection and permission through guardians in case of vulnerable groups and minors, protection of participants' identity, as appropriate to the research and consent. In relation to vulnerable groups and children and young people, researchers will employ proactive measures of safety control (e.g., making sure that children's names or email addresses are not included i.e., are deleted in cases where children misunderstand assignments etc.).

4.1 Interdisciplinary and Multistage Research

GAMEHEARTS addresses significant knowledge and practice gaps through interdisciplinary research involving experts from various fields. Key highlights of the project include:

- Engages world-leading experts from diverse disciplines such as audience research, cultural sociology, games design, gamification, management and business studies, museums studies, media governance, and social policy.
- Addresses gaps in knowledge and working practices through interdisciplinary and multistage research.

4.2 Multi-Sector Engagement

GAMEHEARTS takes a comprehensive approach that extends beyond the EVGIE domain:

- Focuses not only on EVGIE but also places it within the broader context of the Cultural and Creative Industries (CCI).
- Collaborates with industry partners and Advisory Board to understand opportunities and barriers facing the EVGIE.
- Embeds research within wider social, cultural, and policy debates, fostering collaboration among various stakeholders.

4.3 Mixed-Methods and Mixed-Mode Research

GAMEHEARTS approaches data collection and analysis in a diverse and dynamic way:

- Utilising both qualitative and quantitative methods, drawing on established and innovative methodologies, including for instance design thinking marathons.
- Incorporating desk-based research, ethnographic audience research, interviews, focus groups, and user/audience observations.
- Innovatively using games design as a research tool, creating ludic experiences.

4.4 Practice-Led Research with Case Studies

GAMEHEARTS carries out practice-led research, leveraging strategic collaborations with esteemed cultural partners:

- Employing practice-led research with purposefully selected cultural partners (IWM, LSO, CFG) for their global significance and varied engagement with video games.
- Utilising case studies to explore Esports, game engines, preservation of video games, XR, and the metaverse.
- Recognising the importance of strong links between cultural partners and other European and global networks.

4.5 Multi-Informant Approach and Stakeholder Engagement

GAMEHEARTS is dedicated to a comprehensive understanding of the video game industry and takes an ecosystem perspective, meaning that it:

- Adopts a multi-informant approach, incorporating perspectives from stakeholders at different levels and across multiple countries.
- Examines the EVGIE ecosystem from micro (individual gamers) to macro levels (policymakers and industry associations).
- Recognises the diversity of engagement with video games across European member states, addressing digital deprivation and inclusivity.

The ethical aspects of data collection and processing are central to our project and are outlined in detail below.

4.6 Data Collection and Processing

The ethical aspects of data collection and processing are central to our project. Consent is sought from all participants, and we maintain clear communication about the use of images, videos, and interviews for research purposes. The collected data, including telephone/online or face-to-face interviews, focus groups, workshops, and/or surveys and user/audience observations, will be made available for research purposes, adhering to GDPR rules (here also including the UK Data Protection Act 2018) and research ethics, while considering the aim of the project.

In research involving children and young people, obtaining informed consent from both the participants and their parents or caregivers is paramount, as prescribed by law. This process underscores respect for human dignity, acknowledges young citizens' capacity to articulate their perspectives, and upholds their entitlement to be involved in decisions affecting them. Informed consent ensures that participants understand the research purpose, the research conditions, issues of data protection, participate voluntarily without coercion, and retain the freedom to withdraw at any stage.

In summary, our research project is committed to meeting the highest ethical standards and also strives to tailor its approach to specific considerations, ensuring a comprehensive and customised ethical framework. We fully comply with the EU Charter on Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms, and implement international best practices, emphasising the highest level of protection for all research participants.

This commitment is fortified by the application of the EU Reg. 2016/679 GDPR, including national safeguards dedicated to children's protection, such as abiding by Dutch guidelines from the CCMO (Central Committee on Research Involving Human Subjects) advising against non-essential interviewing of people below the age of 16.

Recruitment, inclusion, and exclusion criteria, and informed consent procedures are developed to ensure transparency and adherence to ethical principles. Research participants, including those in the video game and cultural industries, will be recruited through existing networks. Cultural industry audiences will be sourced from databases where permission has been given. Games testers will be recruited via cultural organisations, and/ or via students and staff at the partner HEIs.

GAMEHEARTS engages in the processing and storage of various types of data essential to our research objectives. This includes personal data, encompassing information such as age, gender, racial or ethnic origin, as well as the opinions of research participants regarding their experiences with video games and cultural phenomena. Where details of age, gender, race, etc. are not applicable to the research, they will not be collected.

Additionally, contact information, including name, institution, work address, telephone number, and email, is collected to facilitate the organisation of activities and the dissemination of project results.

Justification for collecting sensitive personal data will be included in the Description of Action before grant agreement signature, along with comprehensive information on data collection, storage, protection, retention, and destruction procedures to ensure compliance with national and EU legislation.

Additionally, all partners will nominate a Data Protection Officer to oversee data handling practices. Furthermore, our approach emphasises safeguarding personal data through stringent ethical guidelines:

- Partners' procedures for data collection and storage, including methods of storage and exchange, and data safety procedures, are meticulously detailed by a designated Data Protection Officer.
- Demographic information that can be viewed as sensitive personal data (i.e., age, gender etc.) collection leading to identification is strictly avoided, with interview results anonymised in storage and scientific publications to uphold confidentiality.
- Our research topic and methodology are designed to prevent any psychological, social, legal, or other harm to participants. Moreover, individuals with personal or hierarchical links to consortium members are not involved in the investigation techniques.
- To minimise risks, all intended forms of survey research are developed with anonymity or pseudonymity in mind, and results are only published in aggregated form. Research protocols are tailored to national frameworks, ensuring compliance with local regulations.
- Participants retain the right to exercise their data rights at any time, in line with the policies outlined in the research protocol.

5. Ensuring International Ethical Compliance in GAMEHEARTS

In ensuring international ethical compliance within the GAMEHEARTS project, participants affiliated with international organisations (IOs) are obligated to adhere to specific principles outlined in the Grant Agreement. This includes upholding fundamental rights, ethical principles, environmental and labour standards, as well as rules on classified information, intellectual property rights, visibility of funding, and protection of personal data. Additionally, IO participants must ensure the submission of certificates under Article 24 by utilising independent public officers or external auditors compliant with standards akin to those specified in EU Directive 2006/43/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 May 2006 on statutory audits of annual accounts and consolidated accounts.

Furthermore, IO participants must allow for checks, reviews, audits, and investigations as stipulated in Article 25, conducted by designated bodies in accordance with any existing agreements between them and the EU. Importantly, the Grant Agreement does not waive any privileges or immunities afforded to IO participants under their constituent documents or international law. Special provisions regarding applicable law and dispute settlement are outlined in Article 43 and Data Sheet, Point 5, respectively.

Research will be undertaken in the UK, as well as in EU countries, involving interviews, focus groups, and overt observations, but no additional ethical issues arise from this. Research activities undertaken in the UK are allowed in EU member states.

Additionally, some communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities, and some consortium meetings will be in the UK.

It is planned to export some personal contact data from partners in the EU (Austria, Poland, Finland, The Netherlands and France) to the UK, with detailed data management outlined in our comprehensive Data Management Plan.

USAL complies with UK and EU GDPR legislation (incl. Data Protection regulation 2016/679). USAL has procedures to protect personal data as well as a Research Ethics Committee.

DISCLAIMER

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